

Volunteer Management of Ruangguru Foundation In Effort to Provide Online Learning Program Assistance for Underprivileged Students in West Java Province

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ABSTRACT: Ruangguru Foundation is an organization that stands under Ruangguru as a form of social mission to the social community. Ruangguru foundation continues to improve access to quality of education through technology that consists of volunteers who work and dedicate their lives to serve the community, by providing online learning assistance for underprivileged students. This study aims to determine the importance of the management of the Ruangguru Foundation in managing each of its volunteers, especially in the online learning assistance program in the West Java region. This study shows that there were obstacles in managing volunteers at Ruangguru Foundation. The employees still need to maximize some elements in management to overcome some problems, such as continual changes of plans that made volunteers have difficulties implementing the programs based on the organization's standards. However, the volunteer feels satisfied if they have done their responsibilities. They feel alive to the fullest for helping people to have a better life.

KEYWORDS: Ruangguru Foundation; Volunteer Management; Volunteer; Online Learning; Leadership

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the important factors in an institution is the people who work in it. Their role becomes very meaningful when a program is implemented to the community or the target of the organization. People who have an important role in the foundations are volunteer workers. This is also meaningful because they are at the forefront of carrying out every preventive and corrective step. This is also important, especially for non-profit organizations because in these organizations they rely on volunteers as the frontline in carrying out every existing program. Volunteers help achieve the organization's mission and achieve more strategic goals. Volunteers provide needed services to these organizations by meeting needs within the organization that cannot be met limited resources by Ronel (2006) such as financial, manpower resources, facilities, and so on. Volunteering in a non-profit organization is not something new because since ancient times our country has been deeply rooted in tradition and practiced in people's lives, especially in rural areas. The form of volunteerism that is most practiced by the Indonesian people, especially is cooperation in construction activities, construction of social facilities, marriage, and death. Youth, parents, and women voluntarily contribute in the form of manpower, money, and facilities according to their components by NGO Circle (2013). The

development of the times and also the issues that occur, cause the role of volunteers to be crucial. Along with the development of non-profit organizations in Indonesia, in the aftermath of the reformation and a series of natural disasters as well as the large quantity of damage compared to previous years, enthusiasm and the spirit of volunteerism (voluntarism) and humanitarian solidarity (genuine solidarity) appear to be increasingly prominent in Indonesia. (NGO Circle, 2013). Becoming a volunteer has its own advantages, which differ from those of materially paid workers. One of the biggest benefits of being a volunteer is that they can help others, getting personal satisfaction because it can mean something to others so that it can increase self-satisfaction according to Brewster & Cerdin (2018).

Behind every volunteer who works, the most important part is the management of the volunteers. The management of the Foundation/Organization is a benchmark for volunteers to carry out their roles well, have clarity on what they are aiming for, have a sense of belonging to what they are doing and also know what goals they will aim for. In organizational management where bureaucracy, organizational structure and clear division of tasks are important for volunteers and even for workers in organizations in general. With management in an organization, bureaucracy is also needed to establish clear domains for their departments, divisions, programs, and units as well as for each employee and volunteer. Ideally, this means that volunteers can function with a certain degree of independence without having to rely on direction from others because there is a clear structure for performing routine daily tasks. According to Peter M Kettner (2013) organizational management responsibilities are intended to help leaders design organizational and human variables in it in a way that suits the unique needs of the organization, staff, and society. The goal should always be to define, design, and define organizational subsystems in a way that ensures that they are internally consistent and support efficiency, effectiveness, quality, and productivity. According to Cheryl Yallen and Barbara Wentworth (2012) there are 3 represent important assessment related. Staffing, planning, and analysis areas in the management and leadership of volunteer activities in an organization. The many benefits and contributions that organisations can give to volunteers in terms of personal development, e-learning voucher, motivations, also rewards. It will empower and encourages all volunteer as unpaid labour have some of meaningful job after all. Above all that, developing and maintaining a successful volunteer resource program also presents challenges, from adequate financial resources and building support from part-time staff, to investing insightful planning in program definition and implementation.

Attached below is the participation of volunteer activities around the world, the table below shows the number of participation of youth aged 15-29 years in volunteer activities worldwide has increased from 2018 to 2021 (Charities Aid Foundation, 2021) and Indonesia in the 1st position for voluntary activity participation among the other countries. Their goal is to enjoy job satisfaction more and get intrinsic personal benefits, because working for non-profit organizations by serving the community makes activities meaningful for their lives according to Selander & Ruuskanen (2016). Volunteers with young age continue to increase from year to year, it can be seen that the needs of the organization are also increasing and need more volunteers to help them perfect the organization's vision and mission.

II. METHODS

To identify volunteer management in Ruangguru Foundation in this study uses: qualitative methods. Qualitative research begins with an idea expressed by research questions (research questions). The location and time of this research was planned intentionally and based on the purpose of this research. The location and time were chosen with the following considerations: West Java Province is a province where the Ruangguru Foundation has the quality of volunteers who are very active, highly participate and are also open to information so that the programs implemented by the Foundation through them can be carried out well and are full of mature initiatives. This province consists of 10 active volunteers who carry out activities for underprivileged communities in the area. Furthermore, the research technique used is purposive sampling. According to Sugiyono (2009: 300) purposive sampling is a data collection technique with certain considerations, for example the person is considered the most knowledgeable and able to become an informant of the information we expect in existing research.

Based on several criteria that the researcher described, in this study the researcher selected informants according to the research objectives, namely knowing the management of the Ruangguru Foundation volunteers to provide learning assistance for underprivileged youth in West Java Province. Furthermore, knowing and identifying the role of volunteers can help the Ruangguru Foundation develop in terms of providing assistance programs for underprivileged youth. Find out how organizational leaders play a role for volunteers in providing learning assistance to underprivileged youth. After that, the selection of information is carried out theoretically which is described in the table below: In this study, purposive sampling technique was used because the researcher felt that the informants were the most knowledgeable about the problem to be studied by the researcher. The researcher also interviewed the stakeholders as informants with reason details as follow:

Table 1. List of Stakeholders

No	Stakeholders	Reason
1	Ruangguru Foundation Volunteer (West Java)	The main subject is the volunteers. So they are very influential and crucial for this research so the comprehensive information as valid sources.
2	Ruangguru Foundation Project Lead	Project lead who leads the volunteer and gives direction, managing the volunteer and creating a management system for volunteers.

3	Ruangguru Foundation Project Officer	Project officer who runs all the programs with volunteers especially for giving support assistance for underprivileged students.
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Source: Process Resourced (2022)

In this study, researcher used in-depth interviews which included semi-structured and unstructured interviews. Sutopo (2006: 72) defined in-depth interview as the process of gathering information for research goals by delivering question and answer where the process is carried out face-to-face between the interviewer and the informant or person being interviewed, with or without using a guide. interview, where the interviewer and informant are involved in a relatively long social life. In addition to the interview method, qualitative research can also use the observation method. According to Zainal Arifin (Kristanto, 2018), "observation is a process that is preceded by observation and then systematic, logical, objective, and rational recording of various phenomena in actual situations, as well as artificial situations".

III. DISCUSSION

Based on results in the field, the following important key points are:

1. Important Elements in The Organization that Managers Need to Pay Attention in Managing Volunteers

In terms of management according to Petter M Kettner (2013), there are several definitions. The definition says that management is the process of planning, organizing, controlling, and leading the various efforts of members of the organization and using all organizational resources to achieve goals. The element to manage the volunteers are : First, Planning. Planning means we have to understand the organization as a system with inputs, outputs, outputs, results, feedback, and with many subsystems. Understand the need for flexible, precise and analytically based organizational structures. Second, Organizing. In this step, Understand the importance of the organizational environment, define mission, goals and objectives, understand the importance of quality, Ensure that the job design is carefully crafted and well planned, consistent also with the given job description and performance evaluation system. monitor, evaluate and conduct research as well. Third, Directing (Controlling). This step means maximizing the use of technology. Last step is Leading. It means Introducing an internally consistent motivation and reward system and understanding the importance of system-wide internal consistency. Another definition by George R. Terry, management is a framework or framework that involves guiding or directing a group of organizational goals or real goals. The management function itself is a series of various activities that are decided together and have a mutual relationship between one another carried out by people in the organization or parts assigned to carry out these activities. Management functions are as diverse as planning, organizing, coordinating, directing, motivating, communicating, leadership, risk taking, decision making and monitoring. If viewed from the existing management process involved the main functions displayed by a manager/leader, namely: planning (planning), organizing (organizing), structuring employees (staffing), leading (leading), motivating (motivating), providing directing, facilitating, empowering staff (empowering) and controlling (controlling). Therefore, management is defined as the process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling organizational efforts with all its aspects so that organizational goals are achieved effectively and efficiently. Effective in this case means doing the right job according to the provisions (doing the right things), while efficient means doing the right thing (doing things right).

According to Cheryle Yallen and Barbara Wentworth (2012 intended volunteer management is also useful for helping managers design organizational and human variables in a way that suits the unique needs of the organization, staff, and society. The manager's goal should always be to define, design, and build organizational subsystems). in a way that ensures that they are internally consistent and promote efficiency. Furthermore, policies

and procedures within management are also needed. Some important risk management tools, on the other hand, also increase the effectiveness of volunteer engagement and the management of volunteer programs by communicating values and beliefs, articulating rules, to identify standards and expectations, all of which support the work of individual volunteers while increasing volunteer productivity, safety, and satisfaction.

Diversity management and empowerment management are processes and outcomes. As a process, diversity management involves the skills, strategies and techniques used to ensure that all workers are managed in a fair and equitable manner. Which in this case, all the volunteer comes from various locations in Jawa Barat (Depok, Bogor, Bandung) and also all activity mostly in online basis. At this research, the volunteers are scattered in various areas and from different education backgrounds with very varied diversity. Effective diversity management can produce stable workers who are committed to the organization. Schmid (2002), in reviewing the literature on the nature of organizations and organizational effectiveness, it found a positive correlation between workers' perceptions of fair rewards and trust in management that they are working for.

According to field data, leading is the important element for volunteering in the Ruangguru foundation. One of the biggest reasons they stayed became the volunteers because they see someone that they can look up to and also part of appreciation of rewards also becomes an important part of volunteering. In terms of their division lead, community officer, community lead and also the other volunteers. Management in Ruangguru's foundation management was established 2 years ago and the foundation still finds the right patterns to implement these volunteering programs. This is also affected by the existence of a volunteer program that changes frequently in the past 2 years, then once the leaders already find the patterns on how to lead, how to implement the program, numbers of turn over volunteers progressively decrease. This has resulted in a high turnover rate for volunteers' reasons no longer because of unclear direction, expectation or implementation from the foundation but due to personal issues (such as, focus for study in college, there is no more volunteering time and so on). More than that, the volunteers are still satisfied to do their responsibility because they can help others and there is an impact resulting from their work, namely being able to help other people in need, especially in the field of education. Even though Ruangguru's volunteer management also feels a challenge when dealing with volunteers who are out of town, especially during the pandemic, all of which are online communication sometimes they can't be contacted, unreachable. For this reason, several things done by the management of Ruangguru are holding online events (organizing the team) to strengthen relationships among the volunteers and also provide meaningful rewards and appreciation for volunteers, for example giving 'volunteer of the month' rewards for volunteers who make a big contribution to the Foundation. The volunteers were also given online training for improving their soft and hard skills, such as communication / public speaking webinar, content writing workshop, creative design / visual workshop and so on. The importance of motivation, praise, appreciation is an important factor for volunteers to maximize their role and responsibilities to the organization. The values in this approach become clearer and more important when presented to volunteers whose rewards are not money but fulfillment of their intrinsic motivation.

2. Leadership Plays an Important Role in Volunteer Management

According to Yeheskel Hasenfeld (2010) there are four quadrants of leadership in organizations. Based on the table above, there are four quadrants of leadership and management patterns in organizations including several types: First, Task-oriented internal. In the type of leadership that is less concerned with results/tasks than the relationship with people themselves, the most relevant leadership pattern is defined by high-level responsible authorities, with very high use of formal power and staff contribution as well. This type of leadership focuses on careful planning, coordination, providing direction, control and supervision, and is also closely related to every process carried out as well as results. Second, People-oriented internal. In the stages of an organization's life cycle, the pattern described in quadrant II is most appropriate. Furthermore, once formed, the leader must focus on developing organizational systems and organizational activities, as well as developing and developing administrative and professional teams. In this of organizational development need to mention that there is no clear pattern of activities,

and the leaders make the activities of one person, where the direction requires organizational members. In the next stage, relying on the knowledge and information possessed by staff members in the decision-making process. For this reason, community service organizations require a division of labour based on the delegation of tasks and the utilization of the relative advantages of team members who specialize in various fields. The focus of this type of leadership is selecting, developing, selecting, building, and leading employees to achieve organizational goals. Third, Task-oriented external. The leadership style described in quadrant III describes how the organization achieves its goals and gains legitimacy and resources from the external environment. With leadership traits, have full authority, directive, sharp focus to get the goal and don't think too much about people as the main factor. Humans as resources are only used as a means to achieve organizational goals. In this quadrant, decision making also comes from the main leader. Last one, External people-oriented type .At the next stage in the development of community service, it is hoped that there will be a change in leadership style. Undoubtedly, leaders must seek organizational structure from and need to focus on positioning the organization and ensuring a steady flow of resources in a dynamic and volatile political environment. The most appropriate leadership pattern at a later stage of development is the pattern described in quadrant IV. In this type of leadership, great leaders focus on the contribution of human resources as an important factor. capacity of workers and build cooperation with other parties to achieve common goals.

Volunteers need a leader who can lead them to do their job well. Especially in this study, the research location is in West Java. Volunteers in this area cover Bogor, Depok, Bandung and surrounding areas. This large area coverage makes it quite difficult for volunteers to monitor their beneficiaries' students. Because supervising volunteers also held important processes in management. Supervision of volunteer workers is important so that they clearly understand the goals to be achieved from an organization according to the right path. According to Karen M. Hopkins (1997) supervision that comes from volunteer supervisors has a direct impact on organizational success through the management of their voluntary employees and employees within the organization. If supervisors are competent, supportive, and demonstrate effective coaching and mentoring practices, employees are more likely to perceive the organization as concerned with employee development and a satisfactory workplace. Effective supervision of volunteers has a direct impact on job performance. One of the things the leaders do is help them by facilitating them, one thing to do is by conducting online meetings for program synchronization, event implementation and also monitoring of each volunteer activity. The volunteers also need leaders with clarity and build connectivity among the volunteers. Some volunteers said that in the last 2 years, a lot of changes happened in terms of structure, leadership, and job responsibility. Volunteering participations are divided into two batches a year, if the volunteer is satisfied with the program typically the will continue to next batch. Usually, they were happy and satisfied because they can connect with the other volunteers, they got rewards and appreciation (online learning voucher, e-wallet, volunteer of the month). They were said to feel happiness beyond words of doing this voluntary activity because they can help others, giving assistance for an underprivileged student and giving for others through their time, energy, effort, skills and knowledge. Even with so many changes back then, they still survive by helping others. They said that Ruangguru's foundation has a great leader to lead the team, the leaders gave help and favor to them, ideas, creating bonding time among the volunteers and also appreciating them through awards.

3. Online Learning Assistance and Other Facilities are Valuable for Volunteers to Help Underprivileged Students

Based on the following are the 4 dimensions according to J. Steven Ott, Dicke Lisa (2015). There are 4 Key Dimensions of Volunteering:

- Voluntary activities

In this case, the volunteers carry out all the responsibilities that they do not based on purely monetary motivation but because they have an inner motivation where they do it sincerely. The main goal is not

to pursue something material but moral value for their life as a volunteer.

- Rewards

The rewards obtained are not in the form of money but in benefits for their own development. Some do it because they want their life to be more meaningful, give more value to others, help others because there is a certain satisfaction for them when doing these volunteer activities.

- Providing Support

Support should be given to volunteers by the organization that supports them, assistance for training, workshops and training related to their activities should be provided by the organization. For example, training on public speaking, the right way of communicating is also needed by volunteers because they will often deal with various kinds of people. It also will help volunteers to having personal development.

- Beneficiaries

Of course, when you become a volunteer, there must be beneficiaries. Beneficiaries can be diverse, with various backgrounds, ages, occupations, and regions. Beneficiaries are usually defined by the organization, so that volunteers can implement aid appropriately.

This online learning assistance is the main activity for Ruangguru volunteers. It begins with fundraising to donors by volunteers, they select the donors, select targets/beneficiaries to be assisted and the destination (in this study, West Java). In this era of covid, all learning assistance is done boldly. Whether it's in the form of learning data packages, cellphones, Ruangguru online learning (product name: ruangbelajar), online class English and Sundanese lessons are also available for those in need. The foundation also gives donations in the form of facilities for schools, one of the initiatives from Ruangguru as a form of their concern for the educational challenges faced by students and educators. It connects aid providers/donor with students or education actors who need assistance with access, support for learning facilities, and quality educational content. The role of volunteers also participates in providing assistance, assessment, and also increasing capacity. As a companion role by Bilal (2020) volunteers have a very strategic role in the implementation of social welfare. Online learning assistance is usually done three times a week via Zoom and after the volunteers teach, they also give homework to students to assess their level of understanding of the lesson. From the things above, the volunteers seem to feel a sense of satisfaction and having 'personal reward' when they can help these underprivileged students. Volunteers are unpaid labor so their satisfaction is not rewarded by money, not only thinking about themselves but how they can help others. Underprivileged students who are accepted this aid, usually they are those who don't have any online connection to internet/digital learning, it becomes one of challenges that they face when giving this online learning. Due to these conditions, kind of support aid form are handphone, data package and for sure guidance to using it. It can also refer to the role of volunteers in providing positive lessons and benefits that lead to greater opportunities to increase student self-actualization. Furthermore, the role of volunteers also helps empower groups in need. According to Mardikanto and Poerwoko (2015) the purpose of empowerment includes various improvement efforts needed including; Improving education means that empowerment must obtain better final results after this empowerment at this case help the underprivileged students to learn English in certain days. This education improvement is carried out through empowerment which is not only limited to improving classes, facilities, material infrastructure, improving methods, but also relating to teaching staff, facilitators and beneficiaries.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of this research, it shows that volunteer management of Ruangguru Foundation has not fully run optimally. This is due to several factors; The program changes quite often, causing the volunteers to feel that there is no clarity so that the turnover rate is high. Second, their expectation when becoming a volunteer is to carry out direct activities with the target beneficiaries, but due to covid-19, circumstances require them to conduct online programs so that they feel that there is a lack of touch points with the target recipients of this bold learning aid. Third, the role of the leader is very meaningful for them to provide direction and also training to develop their skills. Volunteers feel very happy when they can develop their abilities, one of the rewards given when volunteering at Ruangguru Foundation is that they are free to study online at skill academy online learning vouchers which they can exchange for any class and are free as a form of appreciation and reward for volunteers. The must have elements of manager in Ruangguru foundation from organizing , planning, controlling and leading seems implemented well by officer and leaders from year to year.

However, many of the challenges faced by the Foundation's management (community leads and working project officers) when leading the volunteers spread across many areas in online interactions even until now all the activity they never met each other in person. The biggest challenge is managing the volunteers to keep running the program from the Foundation but also to have commitment and consistency to their respective responsibilities. That's why currently they have regulations for termination letters for volunteers who can't be contacted for 3x in a week. Rate of turnover of volunteers at the Foundation (which occurred in the early days of its establishment) is a valuable and learning lesson for employees at the Foundation to build volunteer management to be better.. In a way to build better communication, build bonding time, appreciation, rewarding to volunteers, provide rewards commensurate with their efforts and also provide facilities where volunteers can build connections with other volunteers outside their own region.

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